

Supporting niche formats and hardware in open source software and operating systems

Kieran Kunhya <kieran@kunhya.com> - @kierank_

Who am I?

- Work on Open Source Multimedia in both a personal and professional capacity: FFmpeg and x264 in particular.
 - Also interested in reverse engineering of codecs and hardware
 - Presentation in reverse chronological order for ease of understanding
 - **This presentation given in a personal capacity**
-

Why FFmpeg?

- De-facto open source multimedia processing tool and library
 - Many web browsers implement complex specifications like HTML and CSS
 - Nothing comparable in multimedia
 - Basis of video players such as VLC, browsers (Chrome + Firefox), Smart TVs etc
- Written in C, not in newfangled language of the week
 - Widely supported across computer architectures
 - Likely tens of decades or more of support
 - Works on RPI, watch, other weird device

Standing on the Shoulders of Giants

- Kostya Shishkov and Paul Mahol
 - Master codec reverse engineers
 - Willingness to teach and help (in their own special way...)
 - Both reverse engineered dozens of codecs
 - Monumental impact on media playback
-

Why support niche formats

- Someday, someone might discover and want to play these formats.
 - An impact now or long into the future
 - Most of you in the room are that impact
 - Quite a lot of multimedia low-hanging fruit is “done”, good way to stay familiar with concepts (entropy coding, DCT).
 - Something you can do over Easter/Christmas.
 - Also work for new students
-

This ticket

- There are so many variants of MPEG-4, why are these ones not supported?
- Why are they 4:2:2 and 4:4:4?
- Only 3 samples available, to this day no real-world samples found.

#4447 closed enhancement (fixed)

Opened 4 years ago

Closed 7 months ago

Support MPEG-4 Studio Profile

Reported by:	cehoyos	Owned by:	
Priority:	wish	Component:	avcodec
Version:	git-master	Keywords:	sstp
Cc:	kierank	Blocked By:	
Blocking:		Reproduced by developer:	no
Analyzed by developer:	no		

Description

↳ <http://ffmpeg.org/pipermail/libav-user/2015-February/007875.html>

A user provided three MPEG-4 Simple Studio Profile files that are not supported by FFmpeg.

23.98p SR Lite (4:2:2 @ 220 Mbps)

```
$ ffmpeg -i A003C002_SR_Lite_23.98p.mxf
ffmpeg version N-71321-g6fd300a Copyright (c) 2000-2015 the FFmpeg developers
built with gcc 4.7 (SUSE Linux)
configuration: --enable-gpl
libavutil      54. 22.100 / 54. 22.100
libavcodec     56. 34.100 / 56. 34.100
libavformat    56. 30.100 / 56. 30.100
libavdevice    56.  4.100 / 56.  4.100
libavfilter     5. 13.101 /  5. 13.101
libswscale     3.  1.101 /  3.  1.101
libswresample  1.  1.100 /  1.  1.100
```

MPEG-4 Sstp (1)

- Spent a lot of time trawling the internet looking for recent copy of paid spec
 - Common in industry but a big problem for independent developers.
 - Eventually found it on some Chinese website
 - Woah this is different
 - Up to 12-bit data, 4:2:2, 4:4:4, RGB – none supported in existing MPEG-4 code
 - > 16-bit coefficients (not supported in FFmpeg IDCT)
 - Crazy DPCM mode with vertical block scanning
 - Only one program on Windows, no ability to extract raw data
-

MPEG-4 Sstp (2)

- Entropy coding nice, either works or it doesn't
- Used float IDCT to get to working picture
- No reference decoder, tweaked picture until it looked ok.
- Took another year to get round to boring work of implementing templated integer IDCT.
- Also tedious work to hack-in 10/12-bit into FFmpeg, not ideal method.

MPEG-4 Sstp (3)

- Was quite hard to verify DPCM blocks
- After a lot of digging online found conformance MPEG bitstreams, weird raw file format.
- Got to position where nearly all of image worked but some part looked weird.
- After even more digging found reference software. Typo found: $-(x \gg n) \neq ((-x) \gg n)$
- Might be some minor errors, probably IDCT precision problem, maybe > 32 -bit intermediates?

This press release

Cineform (2)

- Continue reverse engineering tags, lots of people contributed samples.
 - Aligned coefficient layout
 - Simple and fast codec
 - Eventually get to working decoder
- Some samples had more complicated structures, “3D-transform” frames, interlaced, bayer.

Cineform (3)

- https://medium.com/@kierank_/reverse-engineering-the-gopro-cineform-codec-7411312bfe1c – 36k readers!
- Eventually led to Cineform being open-sourced by GoPro!
- Few missing pieces implemented by Google Summer of Code 2018 student
 - Not integrated into FFmpeg yet

But what about Physical Media files come on

- One day someone will come across these and wonder how to read files
 - Panasonic P2 and Sony SxS cards
 - PCI and PCI Express-based respectively
 - Both common and widely used, precursors to modern NVMe storage
 - Closed source Windows and Mac drivers, or proprietary readers.
 - Likely won't work in 100 years
 - Linux driver will last, nothing comparable hardware support
-

Panasonic P2 (1)

- PCMCIA based solid stage storage introduced in 2004
- Modern PCI Express backwards compatible with legacy PCI
- Bought cheap card off eBay.

Panasonic P2 (2)

- Request source code for Linux on camera
 - Dig through thousands of lines and find ancient Linux 2.4 driver.
- Go to parents house, find my high school PC from 2008 with legacy PCI slot.
 - Will it work without official hardware?
- A lot of messing with CentOS and wow, it worked!
- Might have newer cameras with more reasonable driver:
 - <https://github.com/kierank/p2card>

```
total 3488288
dr-xr-xr-x 2 root root    32768 Sep 21  2006
dr-xr-xr-x 8 root root    32768 Sep 17  2006
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 331808992 Sep 17  2006 00109x.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 315104992 Sep 17  2006 0014w1.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 305312992 Sep 17  2006 00157h.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 377888992 Sep 17  2006 0017gb.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root  48992992 Sep 17  2006 00181n.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 438944992 Sep 17  2006 002121.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 445280992 Sep 17  2006 0023h3.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 597920992 Sep 17  2006 0024vz.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 168224992 Sep 21  2006 0025v7.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root  66848992 Sep 21  2006 0026wc.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root  71456992 Sep 21  2006 00276q.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 180896992 Sep 21  2006 0028nw.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root  75488992 Sep 21  2006 0029b7.mxf
-r-xr-xr-x 1 root root 147488992 Sep 21  2006 00301c.mxf
[root@localhost video]# df -h
Filesystem      Size  Used Avail Use% Mounted on
/dev/mapper/Vo1Group00-LogVol00
                3.5G  1.7G  1.7G  50% /
/dev/sda1       99M   19M   76M  20% /boot
tmpfs           1.5G     0   1.5G   0% /dev/shm
/dev/spda1      3.6G  3.6G   58M  99% /mnt
[root@localhost video]# _
```

Sony SxS

- Also requested source code, no driver to be found ☹
- Instead looked into reverse engineering.
- Built rig to easily use card.
- Setup Windows XP QEMU to sniff memory mapped IO, how the driver is reading memory from the card.
 - <https://hakzsam.wordpress.com/2015/02/21/471/>

Sony SxS (2)

- At the time needed newest CPU with IOMMU
 - Use “dd” to read block by block and see how the driver reads and writes. Change the block index, and continue
 - Very basic by modern NVMe standards
 - Request block, get an interrupt with buffer
 - <https://github.com/kierank/sxs-linux>
 - No working DMA yet so very slow
 - Need time to get it into mainline Linux (Christmas?)
-

Conclusions

- Audio and Video codec reverse engineering is tending to completion
 - Codecs are being reverse engineered at a faster rate than they are created
 - This has remarkable historical consequences for media
 - Both the fact that users can “store” their content on sites like YouTube
 - Or that discovered media will be playable for decades
 - That said there are still many proprietary storage formats out there
 - May not be easily possible to use commodity reader and reverse engineer
-